

*REPRESENTATIONS OF WAR,
ON THE REGIONAL
PUPPET
STAGE*

*A Case Study of the Military Repertoire of L'Théât' Louis
(Roubaix, France)*

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ABSTRACT

Despite its richness and the relevance of the issues it raises, the military repertoire for puppets has been the subject of very few studies, and none has focused on the French repertoire prior to 1914. This article focuses on the military repertoire of L' 'Théât' Louis (Roubaix), created by Louis Richard (1850–1915) in 1884, which serves as a case study for examining representations of war on popular puppet stages. In particular, it analyses representations of two types of war: national war, using the example of the Franco-Prussian War (1870–71), and international war, using the example of the Second Boer War (1899–1902). To deepen the analysis, the article proposes to open up the reflection to a regional perspective.

RÉSUMÉ

Malgré sa richesse et la pertinence des questions qu'il soulève, le répertoire militaire pour marionnettes a fait l'objet de très peu d'études, et aucune ne s'est intéressée au répertoire français d'avant 1914. Cet article se concentre sur le répertoire militaire de L' 'Théât' Louis (Roubaix), créé par Louis Richard (1850–1915) en 1884, qui sert d'étude de cas pour examiner les représentations de la guerre sur les scènes de marionnettes populaires. Il analyse en particulier les représentations de deux types de guerre : la guerre nationale, à travers l'exemple de la guerre franco-prussienne (1870–71), et la guerre internationale, à travers l'exemple de la deuxième guerre des Boers (1899–1902). Pour approfondir l'analyse, l'article propose d'ouvrir la réflexion à une perspective régionale.

KEYWORDS

war, puppet theatre, north of France

MOTS-CLÉS

guerre, théâtre de marionnettes, nord de France

Introduction

Despite the prolific corpus of plays that raises important questions of an aesthetic, social, and cultural nature, the military repertoire for puppets and marionettes is the subject of very few specific studies, none of which focuses, to the best of my knowledge, on the French repertoire prior to 1914.¹ However, military life and war were among the favourite themes of French puppeteers in the second half of the nineteenth century, and they were particularly important for the puppet repertoire of northern France. This was characterised, like that of the Sicilian *puppi* or the marionettes of Liège, by a tendency towards chivalric plays. The military repertoire was especially rich in L' Théât' Louis in Roubaix, the region's only traditional puppet theatre, which has managed to pass on its legacy to future generations. Surprisingly, none of the studies devoted to the puppet theatre in northern France has highlighted this richness.² It is this double gap that I seek to begin to fill.

Louis Richard (1850–1915), a textile worker from Roubaix, founded L' Théât' Louis in 1884. It was not his first puppet theatre, but it was the high point of his artistic career.³ Battle dramas greatly enhanced the reputation of the theatre. Léopold Richard (1890–1976), Louis's son, cites among '[t]he typical scenes seen at the Louis theatre around 1900', '[t]he battles where sometimes a hundred or more puppets fell' (Léop. Richard 1961: 13).⁴ He remembers:

In Lille, it was rare to see fights on stage with more than three characters. Everything went on outside. You could hear the clash of swords, the screams, and the play was on! In Louis [theatre], there were also occasional fights outside, but they often continued on stage. (Léop. Richard 1963: 7)

← Léopold Richard at the scene of his booth, c. 1930. Photo by Albert Dervaux-Richard (collected by P. Delannay) © Collections of the Médiathèque de Roubaix, RES APH 8/9

Louis Richard's main aim was to educate his audience of factory workers, most of whom, like him, were of Belgian origin. He had a clear preference for the military history of France, from Charlemagne to Napoleon. His sons, Léopold and especially Maurice (1889–1918), continued in this vein, adding to the repertoire plays about more recent wars, such as the Franco-Prussian War (1870–71). The predominance of the battle theme, not limited to chivalric material, gave this repertoire its distinctive colouring and distinguished it from similar regional puppet traditions. Particularly noteworthy is the choice of modern wars, which were still fresh in the public's memory.

Reflection on the military repertoire raises two key questions. The first is how the figure of the soldier is treated in this repertoire. Is it a heroic or a comic character? The second concerns the representation of battle. What is its place in the play, is it central or peripheral? The case of L' *Théât'* Louis allows us to nuance the analysis by introducing its regional parameters. How strong is its presence in military plays? Is there a dialogue between the military/war reality and the regional issues?

← 1. For studies on the Guignol military repertoire, see Gadagne Musées 2015; Fouillet 2014; Plassard 2022: 83–95.

← 2. See Sibbald 1936; Delannoy 1983; Leroux and Guillemin 1984.

← 3. Louis Richard's career as a puppeteer began about 1860. In 1869, while working in a factory, he opened his first theatre in his aunt's house. The success of L' *Théât'* Louis enabled him to leave his job and become independent. The theatre, closed after Louis's death in 1915, was reopened in 1920 by Léopold Richard, the only son of Louis to return from the First World War. The theatre closed for good in 1941, when Louis's widow died and the family house, of which the theatre was a part, was sold.

← 4. All translations from French in this article are mine.

The Soldier and the Battle in the Popular French Puppet Repertoire

Before I delve into the subject matter, I shall give an overview of the popular French military puppet repertoire of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. The military play, dominated by the figure of Napoleon and the narrative of his campaigns, occupied an important place in the French theatre repertoire of the nineteenth century. The most successful, such as Gaetano Donizetti's *La Fille de Régiment* (The Daughter of the Regiment, 1840), Jacques Offenbach's *La Fille du tambour-major* (The Drum Major's Daughter, 1879), and Victorien Sardou's *Madame Sans-Gêne* (1893), were parodied by the Guignol players. At the same time, original puppet plays about military life were created. In this panorama, I focus on them to show the representation of soldiers and battle on the French puppet stage.

Guignol Joins the Army

France at that time was a nation of two great military defeats, that of Waterloo in 1815 and that of Sedan in 1870. The Battle of Waterloo brought to an end the Napoleonic Wars and caused France to lose its dominant position in Europe. The Battle of Sedan preordained the outcome of the Franco-Prussian War and gave birth to the German Empire on the ruins of the French Empire. These two defeats had considerable consequences for the French army. Conscription, proclaimed in 1793 and formalised by the Jourdan-Delbrel law in 1798, was abolished after Napoleon's fall and the return to power of Louis XVIII (1815). In 1818 military service was re-established, but still with the drawing

of lots and the possibility of being replaced. The war of 1870–71 brought about a major reform of the army, conscription became compulsory for all, and the drawing of lots determined only the duration of service.

The Guignol repertoire of Lyon puppeteers echoes these reforms.⁵ The plot of the classic play *Les Conscrits de 1809* (The Conscripts of 1809) is built around conscription by drawing lots.⁶ Julien, a friend of Guignol's, has drawn the wrong lot and must join the army. As Julien is engaged to Marie, Guignol decides to replace him. In the modern version of the play, the plot does not change, but Guignol, trying to encourage his friend, says 'Every Frenchman was born a soldier' (*Les Conscrits de 1809* n.d.), an almost direct quote of Léon Gambetta's 'when a citizen is born in France, he is born a soldier', said after the inauguration of military service reform in 1871.

5. The Guignol repertoire consists of plays whose plot revolves around a comic situation. In *Guignol marchand de veaux*, for example, Guignol sells his calf to three different customers. This play is part of the so-called traditional Guignol repertoire, a repertoire derived from the improvisations of Laurent Mourguet, the creator of Guignol, and developed by the second and third generations of Guignol puppeteers, in particular Victor-Napoléon Vuillerme-Dunand. Around 1870, puppeteers such as Pierre Rousset began to create what came to be known as the modern Guignol repertoire, which consisted of parodies of plays for actors.

6. I consulted five versions of the play: four manuscripts held in the Musée des Arts de la Marionnette – Gadagne, Lyon (hereafter MAM), *Les Conscrits de 1809* (n.d.); *Les Conscrits de 1809*, manuscript of Vuillerme, Fonds Dor, Box 86, D.141; *Les Conscrits*, manuscript of E. F. Pegay, Fonds Dor, Box 86, D.140 (followed by a typed note indicating that it is not the authentic manuscript of *Les Conscrits*); *Les Conscrits de 1809*, Valentin repertoire, Don Grataloup, (9)98.11.148; and the version published in Jean-Baptiste Onofrio, *Théâtre lyonnais de Guignol*, nouvelle édition, Lyon: Mme Ve Monavon, 1890 [1865], 441–75. None of these versions is dated, but based on the similarities and differences between them, I can assume that Vuillerme's and Onofrio's texts are the oldest, dating from before 1870.

Vuillerme-Dunand, *Le Conscrit*, c. 1853 © Musée des Arts de la Marionnette – Gadagne →

Once a soldier, Guignol must be trained. In *Le Conscrit* (The Conscript) by Vuillerme-Dunand, written around 1853, at the time of conscription by drawing lots, the sergeant shows him the military exercises, which Guignol understands too literally, giving rise to numerous humorous situations.⁷ At the end of the demonstration, while the sergeant goes to fetch a rifle, Guignol decides that 'it's no fun being a soldier' and hits the sergeant with the same rifle. This scene was very popular with Guignol puppeteers, as evidenced by its presence in Tony Tardy's *Les Aventures de Guignol et Gnafron à Tananarive* (The Adventures of Guignol and Gnafron in Tananarive), written some forty years later, in 1896.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, when conscription was for a long time the fate of all young men, the authors of the Guignol repertoire set their sights on another subject — military service — when the comedy focuses on the military hierarchy. *Le Baquet* (The Bucket, c. 1910) occupies a special place among the plays written during this period, presenting military service not as a pleasure but as a source of suffering.⁸ Here Guignol is a poor soldier whose main responsibility is to empty the slop bucket. In trying to get out of doing this task, Guignol creates a series of bizarre situations that lead him back to the starting point. The framing story of conscription disappears because it is no longer necessary. Becoming a soldier is no longer a matter of choice.

7. The only indication of the date is the visa of the Villefranche sub-prefecture dated 25 January 1853 added at the end of the manuscript.

8. The length of Guignol's service, about two years, suggests that the play was written after the Berteaux law of 1905 (which imposed two years of military service) and before the Barthou law of 1913 (which extended service to three years). For plays presenting the military service as a source of pleasure, see *L'Ordonnance embarassé* by Lacoste (1901) and *L'Ordonnance* by Albert Channay (1907).

Le Baquet, c. 1910 © Musée des Arts de la Marionnette – Gadagne →

In the puppet theatres of northern France, the theme of military service is much less popular than in Lyon. I could only find two plays on this subject: Édouard David's *L'Bataille ed Querriu* (The Battle of Querrieu), performed in Amiens (I shall return to it later), and Léopold Richard's one-act comedy (also called *boboche*) in French and Picard *L'Invisible* (The Invisible), based on a script by Louis Richard and played in Roubaix.⁹ The latter recounts the misadventures of Jacques Lenfle, an unenthusiastic reservist unappreciated by his superiors.¹⁰ Dominique, another reservist, wants to make fun of Jacques and tricks him into believing that by magical means, the 'perlimpimpin powder', he can become invisible. Jacques likes the idea: if he is invisible, he will be able to avoid the military exercises, not salute his commanders, eat the tastiest morsels at mealtimes, and do whatever he wants during the twenty-eight remaining days of his service. As the other soldiers are complicit with Dominique, they manage to convince Jacques of his invisibility. The farce ends when Jacques insults the adjutant, who sends him to prison. It is only then that Jacques realises that he has been fooled.

This play is original in its treatment of relationships in the barracks. Unlike other military puppet plays, it not only deals with the military

9. Édouard David's play *L'Bataille ed Querriu* (n.d.) was first published in 1891, but it was highly probably created in the 1880s. It was first performed by the Amiens puppeteer Casimir Clabaut, known as Zacharie, in the Théâtre du Franc Picard. Léopold Richard's *L'Invisible* (n.d.) mentions twenty-eight days of manoeuvres, which suggests that the original script by Louis Richard was created before the law of 7 August 1913, because this law reduced the duration of reserve service to 15 days. Léopold Richard's version of *L'Invisible* is undated, but we can assume that it was written at the end of the 1920s or the beginning of the 1930s. These plays are also called *bamboches*. I prefer here the term *boboche*, because it suggests a possible connection with the old verb *bober*, which means to trick, since fooling someone is the main driving force of the *boboche* plot. Picard, one of the languages of the play, is a language spoken in the northernmost part of France and Hainaut province in Belgium.

10. Jacques Lenfle is a popular type of the Roubaix puppet theatres.

hierarchy but also with the harassment of a soldier by his comrades. Jacques is the victim of a joke at the instigation of a fellow soldier and with the tacit approval of his immediate superior, Corporal Aujus. When Dominique asks permission to play a prank on Jacques, Aujus replies:

He seems to me indeed just right to play the part. I even think he will make a perfect stooge who will give us a good laugh. I'll turn a blind eye, Dominique, I'll go to the canteen. (Richard, Léopold n.d.: 1)

Even when Jacques addresses Aujus directly in a disrespectful manner, the corporal does not try to interrupt the game but decides to continue his blind-eye policy. Instead of warning his superior and his wife about the joke, he prefers to run away, leaving Jacques, convinced of his invulnerability, to cross the red line.

The main character's revolt against the codes of the army is the traditional subject of Guignol military plays. However, Jacques, who is more placid than Guignol, does not seek direct confrontation with authority. His revolt only becomes possible when he thinks he is invisible. And again, he does not beat his commander but just verbally insults him: 'You think you're dealing with a rookie, you rag-and-bone merchant! Poopoo willy. Tame monkey! Three-legged frog!' (Richard, Léopold n.d.: 7). Whereas Guignol is a prankster, Jacques is a prankster who is the butt of the others' jokes. He resembles the Guignol of *Le Baquet*, a prisoner of the system, rather than the Guignol of *Le Conscrit*, who is freer and can change the rules of the game when he does not like them.

The shift of the subject from *becoming* a soldier to *being* one is even more noticeable in two plays about Polichinelle the soldier, performed by two generations of Guérin puppeteers from Bordeaux, which I see as two versions of the same play, *Polichinelle et Pierrot déserteurs* (Polichinelle and Pierrot Deserters) by Étienne Guérin and Prussiens en

France (Prussians in France) by André Guérin.¹¹ In the first, Polichinelle and Pierrot decide to enlist out of poverty. The play still takes place in the era of the voluntary conscript: both are paid for their enlistment. Polichinelle, who has trained as well as possible, is put on guard duty. Bored, he shouts ‘Fire!’ at every opportunity, until he attracts the wrath of his commander, who is about to punish him. Having no desire to go to prison, Polichinelle decides that he has had enough of the army and goes with his friend to an inn to drink. The second play, written after the Franco-Prussian War, develops the same subject. Polichinelle and Pierrot are going to enlist as they are penniless, but here the author gives a reason for their misfortune: the Prussians have destroyed their houses and killed Polichinelle’s family. The main ingredient of the comedy, the enlistment, disappears, giving way to a series of deadly battles. Polichinelle becomes a brave soldier who stands guard and fights against the Prussians. Whereas in the first play, obviously written before the war of 1870–71, *becoming* a soldier is the main theme, in the second, military service itself, with the patriotic halo it acquired after 1871, is central.

11. Étienne Guérin’s play (n.d.: 66–72) is not dated, but as the notebook in which it is found was filled in gradually over a period of about thirty years, it is highly likely that it was written before 1869, the year of Étienne Guérin’s death, as it appears before the obituary written by André-Paul-Julien Guérin for his father. For the same reason, we can assume that the author is Étienne Guérin. The significant differences between the plays that precede and that follow the obituary support this assumption. I would like to express my gratitude to André Guérin for putting his family archives at my disposal. André Guérin’s play is not dated either. However, the allusions to the war of 1870–71 confirm that it was written after the war had ended.

Fighting on and off the Puppet Stage

This brings me to the issue of the representation of war in puppet theatre. In the Guignol repertoire, which constitutes the prevailing part of military puppet plays I mention above, the battle itself is less attractive to the puppeteer than the situation of conscription or military service. But Guignol is not entirely spared from the war. In Tony Tardy’s *La Prise d’Andrinople* (The Taking of Andrinople, 1912), Guignol goes to the First Balkan War as a volunteer fighter pilot, to help the Bulgarian army (Tardy 1912). Yet no scene in the play shows him fighting. The battle is suggested: at the end of the play, there is a gunfight offstage, the Turks ‘all fall, disappearing as they fall’, and Guignol enters with his friends (Tardy 1912: 83). There is no indication that any of them is holding a weapon. Even when the battle scene takes place on stage, it is still very far from realistic. In *Cheval de Bronze* (The Bronze Horse), a parody by Francisque Savy, Guignol becomes the general of the Chinese army and Gnafron the commander of the artillery that besieges the house of the traitor Boulanzig.¹² The friends have to decide how to attack the enemy, but neither of them has a clue about military matters. When the hour of battle arrives, Guignol flees with his soldiers, and Gnafron shouts ‘Fire!’ and rolls about on the stage. Somehow, it all ends with the victory of Guignol and Gnafron. It seems that before the First World War, Guignol and bloody battle could not coexist in the same play.

The question of the representation of the war of 1870–71 is particularly relevant for future analysis. I therefore propose to focus on it. While the Guignol puppeteers avoided putting it on stage, another regional author decided to confront the issue of its representation in puppet theatre.

12. L’Institut International de la Marionnette (Charleville-Mézières) holds a typed version of the play, in which Annequin is credited as the author. Neither text is dated. If the author is Savy, he could have written the play between 1872 (Guignol mentions the twenty-eight days of reserve service introduced by the 1872 military service law) and 1882 (the year of Savy’s death).

Alongside André Guérin, the Picardian poet Édouard David addresses this war in his play *L’Bataille ed Querriu*. Lafleur is sent into the heart of the battle between the French and the Prussians.¹³ Becoming a soldier almost against his will, he shares with Guignol and Polichinelle the same ignorance of military codes, but here this ignorance is given a tragi-comic nuance. David uses Lafleur’s naivety to reinforce the idea that war ‘is a massacre of innocents’ (David n.d.: 5). It is important to emphasise that, unlike his ‘colleagues’, Lafleur does not receive any training but must learn his new occupation directly on the battlefield. However, he does not enter the fray at the first gunshot. It is only when he learns of the death of his wife Cathérine that he ‘falls on the Prussians’ heads’ (ibid.: 17). The merciless battle he wages against the enemy is summed up in a short stage direction that indicates ‘hand-to-hand combat’ (ibid.). The battle ends with Lafleur falling wounded, holding a flag taken from the enemy. It is the high point of his transformation from Picardy peasant to national hero.

Given the difference in the importance of the battle scene in Guignol’s and Lafleur’s plays, we can assume that the reason for this is that the technique of manipulation limits the range of movement and thus the possibilities of staging a fight scene in the case of Guignol. However, André Guérin’s play *Prussiens en France*, which focuses even more on the battle, was most likely performed with glove puppets.¹⁴ The intrigue is composed as a chain of five ‘great battles’. The first, a grenadier’s battle with a Prussian soldier, ends with the grenadier holding the enemy ‘at the point of his bayonet’. In the second battle, the grenadier is mortally wounded, and the Prussian soldier manages to escape.

¹³. Lafleur is a traditional Amiens marionette.

¹⁴. André Guérin performed with two types of puppets: glove puppets, which he used all year round in a small puppet booth set up in the squares of Bordeaux, and marionettes, with which he played twice a year at the spring and autumn fairs. Polichinelle plays, as far as I know, were only performed with the first type during this period.

In the third battle, a *cantinière* avenges the death of her comrade by killing the Prussian soldier.¹⁵ The last two battles of Polichinelle are described in a somewhat apocalyptic way:

Great battle. Guns loaded with powder-shot. Arrival of all the Prussians. Great battle. Death of the Prussians. Arrival of King Wilhelm and Bismarck. Death of all these great Prussians. The devil takes the Prussians away. (Guérin, André n.d.: 4-5)

Polichinelle fights alone, first against the ordinary soldiers, then against their leaders. However, this is not a realistic war but a sublimation of it into a puppet show. The devil carrying away the corpses of the enemy replaces victory and the Marseillaise. The accentuated puppet aesthetic gives the battle a more naïve tone but also allows for potential criticism of the war by the puppeteer (Kor 2023: 16).

The variety of dramaturgical strategies for presenting the battle is evident even in this brief overview: in Savy’s, David’s, and Guérin’s plays, the battle takes place on stage, while Tardy keeps it behind the scenes; in Savy’s and Tardy’s plays, it is a passing episode, while in David’s and Guérin’s it is the climax of the plot. Yet, as different as they are, these battle scenes are all presented in the naïve tone of a popular puppet play. In all the plays mentioned above, the regional character is the axis around which the plot is built, and the representation of the soldier retains its comic character even against a background of tragic events. In this context, the L’Théât’ Louis’s repertoire, which favours military plays but leaves out regional character (with the exception of *L’Invisible*), is intriguing. What strategies do the Richards use to represent the battle and the soldier? How does the regional aspect come into play, if at all?

¹⁵. A *cantinière* was a woman attached to a military regiment. Her duties included providing food and tobacco for the soldiers and nursing the wounded.

The Military Repertoire of L' Théât' Louis

The repertoire of L' Théât' Louis consisted of *grandes pièces* in French, each with a few dozen acts, and *boboches*. Most of the *grandes pièces* were adaptations of successful popular novels, with a preference for historical subjects. It is important to point out: in Louis Richard's time, all the pieces were rudimentary scripts. After the First World War, Léopold Richard reconstructed them from memory, giving special treatment only to the *boboches*, which he developed into real plays.

In 1904, Maurice Richard, the son of Louis, invented a new genre, *pièce de jeudi* (Thursday play). The Thursday play resembled the *grande pièce* but was shorter, with no more than five acts. The number of characters was also limited (at the beginning, Maurice manipulated the marionettes on his own). Each play was performed only once, so for each Thursday a new script had to be composed.¹⁶ The Thursday plays brought a new audience to the theatre. If Louis performed mainly for adults, Maurice played at the beginning for younger audiences of more or less the same age as himself. However, because of their low price, the Thursday plays soon became popular with adult audiences as well.

In order to examine the dramaturgical strategies used to represent war in the Richards' repertoire, I propose to concentrate on the Thursday plays, which deal with the recent military conflicts, and in particular two wars: one national, the Franco-Prussian War, and the other international, the Second Boer War.

¹⁶ There is one exception to this custom: the play *Le Mystère de Venice* (The Mystery of Venice) was performed twice.

Representing the National War

The Franco-Prussian War left France deeply traumatised because of the defeat at Sedan, the loss of Alsace-Lorraine, and the humiliation of Versailles. To cope with the defeat and to recover from the trauma, several French writers put their pens to the service of the glorification of the heroes, the soldiers, and, first and foremost, the *francs-tireurs*, the civilians who participated alongside the soldiers in the war. A new genre was born, a literature of war, or rather, as Claude Digeon writes, 'a literature of warlike adventures' (1992: 56). An 'adventure full of dramatic interest' (Paul Bert, quoted in Robichon 2017: 112) became the guiding principle, above all, of post-war children's literature, the latter serving the objectives of a new educational system introduced by the Third Republic and oriented towards patriotism and nationalism. It prepared boys to become soldiers, the bearers of revenge presented as unavoidable (Robichon 2017: 111–13).

On the theatrical level, the historical and patriotic drama *Les Martyrs de Strasbourg ou l'Alsace en 1870* (The Martyrs of Strasbourg or Alsace in 1870) by a certain G. Champagne¹⁷ stands out. Banned, authorised, and re-banned by the censors, the story of the confrontation of the *franc-tireur* André and the spy Heinrich (a German who became a French citizen) was performed by theatres throughout France until the First World War. Émile-Isidore Pitou, an itinerant puppeteer famous in the regions of central France, even adapted it for marionettes. But this was the exception that proved the rule: the war of 1870–71 remained little represented on the nineteenth-century French puppet and actor stage. The plays by David and Guérin mentioned above are probably the only ones on the subject written for puppets. For this reason, the

¹⁷ G. Champagne was an itinerant actor whose company was the first to perform the play in the early 1870s.

seven Thursday plays about the war of 1870–71, most of them created by Maurice Richard, offer an opportunity to study the representation of the national war on the regional puppet stage.¹⁸

La Bataille de moulin (The Battle of the Mill, 1906) illustrates well how the Thursday play about the war of 1870–71 looks. The miller Mérindol warns the French that the Prussians housed in his mill want to enter at night Bazeilles, a small village near Sedan. Mormont, a French officer, who is in the village with his men, decides to attack the mill.

The astonished Prussians barricade themselves in the mill. [...] Mormont sends the cavalry on the road to Bazeilles into the wood. But after their departure Mérindol comes to say that the wood is occupied by the Prussians, shells begin to fall and the line retaliates with their chassepots. Mormont sends a rider to warn Carels, but a cannonball takes his head off and his horse gallops away in fear. Then the battle rages.

[Act] 4 - Forest

The French are startled by the appearance of the headless horseman, they are surprised by the Prussian infantry and decimated, but Mormont arrives with the line and a small victory crowns their courage. (Richard, Maurice 1906b: 75)

The manner of writing in this extract suggests the influence of the literary source on Richard. The script of *L’Espion* (The Spy, 1909) offers a no-less poetic description of the battle: ‘After violent fighting the French lose ground and retreat towards the road to Strasbourg’ (Richard, Maurice 1908: 40). And later: ‘[...] the Prussians are beaten into

retreat but only giving ground step by step’ (ibid.: 40). However, as the scripts analysed here are not the original texts used by Maurice Richard during the performance but the texts that his brother Léopold transcribed some ten years later, it is impossible to say to which of the two this particularly poetic style of narration belongs.

The literary influence that characterises all of the Richards’ scripts does not mean that the text is undramatic. On the contrary, and the extract I quoted above illustrates this well. Each descriptive sentence refers to the action on the stage: the Prussian barricade, the cavalry’s departure, the battle. In *La Bataille de moulin*, as in other Thursday plays about the war of 1870–71, battles and fighting scenes form the main part of the narrative, which is made up of attacks and counter-attacks, victories and defeats, linked by a schematic plot. The first attack is usually by the Prussians (except in *Lydéric et Rinaud*, 1906), followed by resistance or an unsuccessful French offensive (forcing the French to retreat), and then by a French attack.

The battle comes to the fore. Richard depicts the war as a conflict between two nations, the Prussians and the French. Against this background, a series of individual actions take place. In *La Bataille de moulin*, the main protagonists are the miller Mormont and the officer Mérindol. Similarly, in *Un héros* (A Hero, 1911), the civilian-military pair represent the French side. André, a French infantryman, mortally wounded by the Prussians, asks the farmer Ribert to accomplish his mission and bring reinforcements to the French surrounded by the enemy army, in the case of his death. André is shot by the enemy, but Ribert manages to warn Lieutenant Desbrée, the commander of the *garde mobile*, who comes with his men and defeats the Prussians.¹⁹

¹⁹. The *garde mobile* was a military unit that gathered together all those who had managed to avoid regular conscription. Created in 1866, it was intended to strengthen the French armed forces in the face of the war with Prussia.

¹⁸. With the exception of *Lydéric et Rinaud* (1906), for which the author’s name is not given.

In another two of Richard's plays, the pair of military personifies the French army: the *cantinier* Biscot and the officer Caron, in *Le Capitaine Caron*, and two French soldiers, in *Lydéric et Rinaud*. The latter tells the story of Lydéric and Rinaud, who were captured trying to steal the enemy's plans and sentenced to death. Saved at the last minute by the intervention of the French army, they join their compatriots on the battlefield. Lydéric is mortally wounded, and Rinaud avenges his death by killing the Prussian general. Lydéric and Rinaud, like Mormont and Mérindol, André and Ribert, Biscot and Caron, together form a heroic figure that contributes to the French victory.

In contrast to the French fighter figure, the Prussian one is not entirely heroic and positive. Here, the pair of the brave soldier and cowardly spy dominates. *L'Espion* portrays the character of the Prussian general Guévan at the heart of the battle:

Guévan triumphs but soon rifle shots are fired at his rear guard. Then caught in the crossfire Guévan dies bravely, the Prussians are beaten into retreat but only giving ground step by step.

(Richard, Maurice 1909: 40)

Guévan dies like a hero, although he is a Prussian. Vaury, who complements him, is executed for spying. I find the same double representation of the enemy in *L'Espion Heygof* (The Spy Heygof, 1906), in which the Prussian general Zuroc dies in battle and the evil spy Heygof replaces him.

In Maurice Richard's plays about the Franco-Prussian War, the battle is not a culmination of the plot, as in the case of Guérin's or David's plays, but the fulcrum around which all the intrigue is built. Surprisingly, however, in none of the seven Thursday plays about the war of

Maurice Richard, *Un héros*, 1911 © Collections de la Médiathèque de Roubaix, www.bn-r.fr →

1870–71 does the battle take on a personal dimension. There are scenes of armies attacking each other, but there are no fights between two individuals. Spies are executed, enemy guards are knocked out, but there is no semi-grotesque combat of the popular type against multiple enemies. The individuals die in the collective battle, killed by an anonymous collective enemy. They contribute to the military effort of their nations: soldiers and civilians, especially on the French side, are happy to die for their country. The scripts thus reflect the patriotic and military education promoted by the Third Republic.

Does the portrayal of the war of 1870–71 in Richard's plays reflect historical truth? On the one hand, the manner of writing, largely influenced by the literary source, gives the war an adventure halo of post-war children's books. In particular, the intrigue of *La Bataille de moulin*, with its scene of the headless horseman, may seem more fantastic than realistic. However, the scene with the headless rider, according to Léopold Richard, was one of the typical scenes acted out by the theatre (1961: 13). On the other hand, the script of *La Bataille de moulin* relates to a real event of the war of 1870–71, the Battle of Bazeilles, fought on 1 September 1870 as part of the larger Battle of Sedan.²⁰ References to the key moments of the war also characterise the other plays. The action of *Lydéric et Rinaud* and of *L'Espion* takes place in Alsace and Lorraine. The intrigue of *Les deux espions* is set against the backdrop of a besieged Paris. In *Un héros* it is the battle of Bapaume that provides the context for the plot. The final of Thursday's plays about the war of 1870–71 is realistic too. The definitive victory of the French is a rare case; more often the plot oscillates between victory and defeat. Thus,

²⁰. As a key moment in the 1870–71 war, the Battle of Bazeilles has left its mark on France's collective memory. Considered a symbol of French heroism and patriotism, it inspired Alphonse de Neuville's famous painting *Les Dernières Cartouches* (1873). At the end of the nineteenth century, the memory of the Battle of Bazeilles entered popular culture with Émile Zola's novel *Le Débâcle* (1892) and the film *Les Dernières Cartouches* by Georges Millières (1897), both inspired by de Neuville's painting.

Le Capitaine Caron ends with the French soldiers being led into battle and singing: 'Victor galvanises his soldiers and leads them singing. They fought a hundred against a thousand! etc... the soldiers sing' (Richard, Maurice 1906c: 48). Richard's approach to the Franco-Prussian War is therefore different from Guérin's. There is no attempt to turn defeat into victory, or at least to give the impression of triumph, as Édouard David does. Nevertheless, the patriotism and nationalism promoted by post-war French literature and education colour the representation of the battle.

Representing the International Military Conflict

Alongside the Franco-Prussian War, another kind of war occupied French minds at the turn of the century: the Second Boer War, 1899–1901, a military conflict between the British and the descendants of Dutch and German settlers in South Africa. Why was there such an interest in a war in which France did not participate? The Fashoda crisis of 1898, after which France was forced to retreat to Sudan in the face of the British, left a feeling of humiliation followed by a wave of anglophobia. Naturally, when the war with the Boers broke out, France supported the enemy of its enemy, seeing in the Boers those who would take its revenge. Thus, the Second Boer War became a burning theme in France, giving rise to a number of plays, including *Au Transvaal* (In the Transvaal, 1899) by Georges Grison and Albert Dupuy, *Boërs, en avant!* (Boers, Forward!, 1901) by G. Grison, Albert Dupuy, and Henri Raymond, and *Les Boërs ou La Guerre de Transvaal* (The Boers or The Transvaal War, 1900) by Fernand Meynet and Georges Fernoux.²¹

²¹. *Au Transvaal* was performed for the first time in Béziers, on 13 February 1900. *Boërs, en avant!* was premiered at the Théâtre Maguéra on 25 November 1900. The date and place of the first performance of *Les Boërs ou La Guerre de Transvaal* are unknown. The first mention I have found in the press is the performance in Tourcoing at the beginning of February 1900 ('Départements', *Gil Blas*, 13 February 1900: 4).

Émile-Isidore Pitou adapted the latter for marionettes.²² The anglo-phobia that was projected in these plays was particularly attractive to the Belgians who lived in France.²³ In Belgium, where both Flemish and Walloons regarded the Boers as ‘racial brothers’, the pro-Boer sentiment was particularly strong. It is not surprising, therefore, that the first show to be staged at L’Théât’ Louis relating to the Second Boer War responded to public demand (Richard, Léopold 1961: 8).²⁴

In the five Thursday plays devoted to the Second Boer War, the dramaturgical strategies for representing of the battle are largely the same as in the plays about the war of 1870–71. Maurice Richard’s description of the battle between the British and the Boer forces surrounding the Boer town of Kimberley in *La Bataille de Kimberley* (The Battle of Kimberley, 1906) mixes poetic description with references to actual events.²⁵ The fierce battle between the two sides occupies two of the four acts of the play: in the third act, the British fight, and in the fourth act, ‘a group of English [manage] to surround and machine-gun the enemy

²². Apart from this performance, I have only found one trace of the Boer War in the puppet theatre, a musical score for the show *Guignol chez les Boërs* (Guignol among the Boers), MAM, Fonds Dor, Box 88.

²³. Thus, for example, the anonymous author of the brief report on *Au Transvaal!* notes that the Belgians were particularly enthusiastic about the victory of the Boers at the end of the play, ‘which made their Anglophobic heart rejoice’ (‘De Charleroi’, *L’Intransigeant*, 13 March 1900: 3).

²⁴. Richard’s Theatre’s first production about the Second Boer War was in 1901, with the *grande pièce* *Le Capitaine Casse-Cou* (Captain Daredevil) by Louis Richard, probably inspired by the novel of the same title by Louis Bousсенard that was published in the *Journal de voyage* between December 1900 and September 1901. Unfortunately, the script of this play has not come down to us.

²⁵. For example, the siege of Kimberley, one of the main Boer towns, by the British Army between October 1899 and February 1900 was one of the most important events of the Second Boer War. The English officer Buller, one of the characters in the play, was probably inspired by the General Sir Redvers Henry Buller (1839–1908), commander-in-chief of the British Army in South Africa during the Second Boer War.

infantry’, but in the end, ‘the Boer cavalry crushes the English’ (Richard, Maurice 1906a: 79). However, *La Bataille de Kimberley* is the only play in which the battle is at the centre of the intrigue. In other plays, the scenic presence of the battle is reduced. In *Héroïsme d’enfant* (Heroism of a Child, 1906), for example, the word ‘battle’ is mentioned in the fourth act, entitled ‘Around Kimberley’, but the text concentrates on the individual actions of the main characters rather than on describing the battle. In *Paul Pother* (1906), the fight between the Boers and the English is a brief episode in the second act.

Indeed, the Thursday plays about the Second Boer War, even more than the Thursday plays about the war of 1870–71, bring the individual act of heroism to the fore. In Léopold Richard’s *Héroïsme d’enfant* (1911), the English make fun of the Boers for being peasants. Then one of English says that this is true, but that the Boers fight like real soldiers.²⁶ The main resistance comes from the men: David, the only Boer spy in *La Bataille de Kimberley*; Paul Pother in the eponymous play; Christian Deroser in *Espoir de vengeance* (Hope of Revenge, 1908). As in the plays about the war of 1870–71, the main character is complemented by a secondary character who helps and, if necessary, replaces him. The one who stands out among them is Caril, Christian’s second. He is the only one who is not a Boer, as he comes from Marseille. In the eyes of the English officer, however, there is not much difference between the Boer and the French: they are both peasants whose language he does not understand. This identification of the Boers with the French in the face of their common enemy is symptomatic of the period in which the play was written.

The particularity of the Thursday plays about the Second Boer War is that the civil struggle involves all ages and both sexes, while the plays

²⁶. It is worth noting that in the novels written at the time about the Second Boer War, the myth of the peasant soldier was widespread (Seillan 2011).

about the war of 1870–71 show only male heroism. In *Héroïsme d'enfant* (1906), Anna Peters, manipulated by the spy Colville, tells him how to get to Kimberley. When she realises his true identity, she fights with him and is killed. Her son Ludovic, aged twelve, avenges her death.

The boy who becomes a war hero is the subject of two plays of the same title, *Héroïsme d'enfant*: one by Maurice Richard (1906) and the other by Léopold Richard (1911). In Maurice's case, Ludovic avenges the death of his parents. The boy appears three times in the play: in the first act he fights with his mother's killer but cannot stop him; in the third act, with a bandaged head, he is mourning the death of his mother when his dead father is brought home on a stretcher. Finally, in the fourth act, he kills Colville, who is responsible for his parents' deaths, but soon afterwards an English bullet pierces his chest. Gaston Roger, in Léopold's play, is a little older, aged fourteen. Gaston is the brave son of a Boer resistance leader. He takes charge of passing on a message to Bardou, the Boer commander. Wounded by the English, he manages to accomplish his mission but dies immediately afterwards. The centrality of the theme of child revolt in these two Thursday plays resonates with youth literature about the Franco-Prussian War. The children who fought, who sacrificed their lives for their country, who had to face the death of their parents and who alone could avenge it, were the main heroes of the novels and stories written for young people in the Third Republic (Robichon 2017: 113). Absent from the Thursday plays about the Franco-Prussian War, the child character finds all its strength here.

Old men resist as well, but passively. Pother in Maurice Richard's *Paul Pother* refuses to give information on the Boer resistance, dies, and becomes a martyr who must be avenged. In Louis Richard's *Espoir de vengeance*, old Deroser is told to leave his home or become British within

Louis Richard, *Espoir de vengeance*, 1908

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dans le jardin du ... siens main et l'avoir vu cacher 3
quelque chose près du puits. Harold va écrire avec ses amis.
Ses Blanche est tué par Serignot d'un coup de pistolet, mais il est pris
et conduit à la Pétrole. Harold revient et reconstruit le mendiant
l'avoir parlé. Matricule et Chévalier auront la somme promise par grand père

3 Espoir de vengeance - de Louis Richard 1908
Christian Deroser son père Harry Charvignac anglais
Gérard Deroser son père des soldats anglais
Caril corrigé il est maraillais les biers

1 Chez Deroser
Il plaint son pays, un anglais vient dire qu'il faut s'en aller ou se
naturaliser anglais dans les 24 heures. Deroser se dit qu'il est chez lui, sa
maison fruit de son travail un lopin de terre qui lui appartient devoir
tout quitter! - Gérard son voisin vient lui dire qu'il a reçu aussi le fameux
ordre - Christian revient et apprenant tout dit que Kruger s'est allié
à l'Orange pour défendre le Transvaal. Christian prêche la résistance
il est acclamé Mort aux anglais

2 Forêt
Caril s'occupe de guerre sans parti pris puis un anglais à qui Caril
parle une langue inconnue, il est pris comme hollandais. Caril le prend
pour un chitchoit. Ils se trouvent bons amis et sont biers. Suit
Harry se dit que bientôt les anglais sont maîtres des mines d'or mais
voyant l'un de ses hommes boire avec un étranger, il les appelle et interroge
Caril qui raconte de plus en plus Harry ne le comprend pas. Il dit à
ses soldats qui aussitôt les payonn. Partis il leur faudra travailler la
terre pour y trouver de l'or. Suit Caril prend parti pour les vobés -
les biers arrivent et se mêlent du français mais ce dernier dit qu'il
est des leurs un seul ne sait pas s'indiviser c'est Deroser.

3 Chez Deroser
Son fils lui fait comprendre qu'il aurait du faire comme les autres
le père refuse tout. Les combattants viennent le supplier de les suivre
sans y parvenir. Deroser reste seul. Suit Harry entre et ne comprend
pas pourquoi il y a résistance. Deroser dit que sa maison est à lui
et il insulte Harry qui le fait fusiller sur place! - Suit la maison
est abandonnée Christian arrive avec Caril qui dit de rendre coup pour
coup malheur aux anglais

4 Roches (bord du camp anglais)
Caril demande à Gérard de l'aider, ils vont couper la corde qui
retient le cheval de Harry, et quand il viendra le chercher Gérard
le tuera! - Suit Harry poursuivant son cheval est tué par Deroser
abrité au coup de feu les biers disparaissent.

5 Forêt
Caril se dit que la guerre n'est pas finie mais que l'issue ne fait
aucun doute, les anglais seront vainqueurs - Christian l'admet mais la
lutte est engagée et chaque anglais qui tombera sera pour lui un
soulagement. Mais soudain les anglais cernent la compagnie française
seul Christian et Caril s'échappent les anglais sont entortillés leurs
morts - Christian va à l'étranger lever des volontaires pour la lutte du droit.

twenty-four hours. His son tries to convince him to leave, but Deroser insists on staying. Like Pother, he insults the enemy and is shot. His death is also avenged. The only old man whose death goes almost unnoticed is that of Henri Roger's father (*Héroïsme d'enfant*, 1911), who is killed in his house during the English attack.

When the soldiers are peasants, the battlefield changes too: the war moves into the house. It is there that Anna and Ludovic Peters beat the spy to prevent him from going to Kimberley, the old men resist the English, and Gaston Roger faces the enemy for the first time. In the play *Héroïsme d'enfant* (1911), the house is given the qualities of a city under siege and attack:

The house under siege, the English attack relentlessly, old Roger falls mortally wounded. A stronger attack and the door gives way, some more Englishmen fall before reaching Henry who is protected by furniture, but he is taken. (Richard, Léopold 1911: 25)

No one tries to defend themselves against the violence of the enemy; the defence will come from the outside. The Boers attack, and the English have to retreat, but then they manage to get in, and take or kill all those who are inside. Indeed, the battle for, or in, the house is always a lost battle.

The general sense of a lost war characterises the war dramaturgy of the Thursday plays dealing with the Second Boer War. In *Paul Pother*, the Boers attack and the English retreat, but in the end the outnumbered enemy pursues the Boers into the forest, surrounding and killing them. Ludovic's death overshadows his revenge: the victory is a Pyrrhic one, everybody dies, both the English and the Boers. Caril says to himself 'that the war is not over but that the outcome is not in doubt, the English will be victorious' (Richard, Léopold, Ms 204: 3). However, *La Bataille de Kimberley* ends with the Boers' victory, and *Héroïsme d'enfant* (1911) closes with the words 'Long live the Transvaal' (Richard, Léopold 1911: 25).

In the Thursday plays devoted to the Franco-Prussian War, the war was portrayed as a confrontation between two nations. Here, by contrast, the emphasis is on the individual struggle for freedom. The heroic act and the martyr's death replace the battle scene, while the emphasis is clearly on the Boers' side, and on their individual sacrifices contributing to the collective effort. This portrayal of the Second Boer War is entirely in keeping with the pro-Boer attitude towards the conflict in France, as reflected in the French press and especially in the literature of the time.²⁷ As Jean-Marie Seillan writes, from a dramaturgical point of view, the Boer war 'made it easy to place individual adventures within a collective history'. And he adds: 'It was also a collective adventure, insofar as the story of the Boers was perceived, in France at least, as that of a people defending its freedom and independence against an illegitimate aggressor: hence the epic tone that was likely to elevate the unknown hero to the rank of spokesman for his people, or even, in the event of failure, of sacrificial victim and martyr' (2011: n.p.).

Representing the War on Regional Stage

Neither in the plays about the year 1870–71 nor in those devoted to the Second Boer War do any regional elements seem to be present. None of the characters is identified as being from Roubaix or the north of France, or at least as speaking Picardian. The miller Mérindol clearly states: 'I am French and work for my country!' (Richard, Maurice 1906b: 75). Moreover, unlike other popular military puppet repertoires, Richard's does not focus on the regional comic type, Jacques Lenfle. Is it justified to claim that the regional character of the theatre had no influence on the representation of the war, whether national or international, in the case of L' Théât' Louis? And if not, how does their regional character come to the fore in this case?

²⁷. See Latour 2021; Seillan 2011.

The clearest evidence of the regional presence are the names of the main characters in *Lydéric et Rinaud*, which allude to heroes from the popular legends of northern France: Lydéric refers to the founder of the city of Lille, and Rinaud to Renaud de Montauban, one of the four Aymon sons. The legend of Lydéric, like the story of the four sons of Aymon, is inextricably linked to the regional identity of northern France.

However, it is mainly the references to Belgium that evoke the regional aspect. Thus, the character of Marc Dévis in *L'Espion Heygof*, who smuggles gunpowder from Belgium to help fight the Prussians, suggests that the action of the play takes place near Roubaix, a town on the Franco-Belgian border. Moreover, Dévis is a clear nod to Richard's audience, most of whom were of Belgian origin.

If Maurice Richard does not go beyond the allusion here, his father takes the Belgian aspect much further. In *Espoir de vengeance*, for example, the British order the Boers to leave their homes or accept British citizenship within twenty-four hours. This cruel, unjust, and resistance-inducing decree was totally invented. In reality, it was the British who wanted to become Boers. So why did the author reverse the order of things? Because such a naturalisation did take place, but in France. In 1889, the new naturalisation law was introduced, allowing children born to foreign parents but resident on French territory to be naturalised when they reach the age of majority. Its main aim was to increase the number of French soldiers in order to avoid another defeat like that of 1871. This law affected the lives of many foreigners living in France, in particular Belgians, who constituted the greater part of Richard's spectators. It also became the catalyst for the transformation of Roubaix from a town of Belgian immigrants to a French city.

This change immediately affected the repertoire of L' 'Théât' Louis, especially its regional component, the *boboche*. In 1898, a part of the public

demanded the replacement of the comic Picard play by a one-act play in French (Richard, Léopold 1961: 10). In all likelihood, the spectators who called for the abolition of the *boboche* were young men who had been naturalised as French by the law of 1889 and who had grown up in the educational system of the Third Republic, which promoted the French language and banned regional dialects from schools. Paradoxically, the resurrection of *boboche* plays coincides with the emergence of the Thursday plays, intended originally for a young audience.

Léopold Richard's *Héroïsme d'enfant* also raises the question of national conversion. In the play, the English officer Golden suggests that the Boer Henri should 'change his smock for an English uniform' (Richard, Léopold 1911: 25). Even though this is not a forced conversion, but a proposal to change sides addressed to an individual, it has a symbolic meaning. If Henry, the leader of the Boer resistance, renounces his identity and joins the English army, it will automatically mean the conversion of all Boers to the English side. The pro-Boer propaganda against British imperialism shapes here, as in other plays, the portrayal of the war as a fight for freedom. The Boer slogan that ends the first act of the play, 'Live Free or Die', confirms this.

The regional references in Richard's military plays, especially those dealing with the Second Boer War, suggest another interpretation of this anti-imperialistic spirit. It is quite possible that this was the Richards' way of speaking out against the overwhelming domination of French nationalism over a regional minority, a domination that a Roubaix puppeteer and his audience had to face every day. This brings me back to the names Lydéric and Rinaud discussed above, as they both refer to characters who rebel against the injustice of the governor and thus oppose the dominant political power.

Léopold Richard with the heroes of the *boboche* on his right (Jacques closest to him) and those of the *grande pièce* on his left. Photo by Albert Dervaux-Richard (collected by P. Delannay) © Collections of the Médiathèque de Roubaix, RES APH 8/9

If in the popular military puppet repertoire there is always a type like Lafleur or Polichinelle, the quintessence of the fighting spirit of the French army in the face of the enemy, the Thursday plays of L' Théât' Louis offer something new. Rather than involve regional types in national and international military conflicts and thereby give them a local flavour, the Richards use national and especially international war as a vehicle to talk about regional issues.

Conclusion

The wars that took place in the second half of the nineteenth century and at the beginning of the twentieth century inspired the new repertoire of popular puppet theatres in France. Among them, the repertoire of L' Théât' Louis stands out for its completely different approach to the representation of the soldier and the battle. The soldier is not the regional comic type but the double fighting figure, more literary than dramatic. The battle, in turn, occupies a central place, being the driving force of the plot, which unfolds around characters embodying ideas of patriotism and heroism.

In this respect, the Thursday plays on the war of 1870–71 are closer to the spirit of national education at the time than to the spirit of popular theatre. But it is not yet a tool for 'brainwashing', or for 'nationalist, warmongering and racist propaganda' (Plassard 2022: 92). The naïve plots involving spies, smugglers, soldiers, and brave boys are more reminiscent of warlike adventure literature than the military Guignol plays of the First World War.

While the Franco-Prussian War fits in with the French military narrative that Louis Richard wanted to convey to his audience, the Thursday

plays devoted to the Second Boer War resonate with the regional sentiment and the anglophobia of the spectators of Belgian origin. They put therefore the fight for freedom and the revolt against the imperialist army in the foreground. Certainly, the pro-Boer feelings had a major influence on the way the Richards portrayed the war. But I think they go further, identifying the Boers' struggle with their own, the revolt against British imperialism with the fight against French nationalism.

Thus, it is above all the position of the Richards' plays at the intersection of the national and the regional, and their potentially regional reading of international military conflicts, that makes them worthy of scholarly attention and gives them a special relevance for our own times.

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L' Théât' Louis booth, c. 1930 →

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